

Chromium(III) and manganese(II) complexes of macrocyclic ligand containing thiosemicarbazide moiety : Spectroscopic and biological studies

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Abstract : Complexes of Cr^{III} and Mn^{II} were synthesized with a macrocyclic ligand i.e. 5,6,11,12-tetrafulyl-3,8-dithione-1,2,4,7,9,10-hexaazacyclododeca-1,4,6,10-tetraene. The ligand (L) was prepared by [2+2] condensation of furil and thiosemicarbazide. Their structures were determined by the elemental analyses, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility measurements, Mass, IR, electronic and EPR spectral studies. Molar conductance measurement shows that Cr^{III} complexes are 1 : 1 electrolytes whereas Mn^{II} complexes are non-electrolytic in nature. Thus the complexes may be formulated as [Cr(L)X₂]X and [Mn(L)X₂] [where X = Cl⁻ and NO₃⁻]. All the complexes of Cr^{III} and Mn^{II} are of high spin type and showing the magnetic moment corresponding to three and five unpaired electrons, respectively. On the basis of IR, electronic and EPR spectral studies an octahedral geometry has been assigned for these complexes. *In vitro* the synthesized compounds were screened against several species of plantpathogenic fungi.

Keywords : Macrocyclic, chromium(III), manganese(II), spectral, biological screening.

Introduction

The synthesis and structural investigation of thiosemicarbazones and their metal complexes are of considerable centre of attention because of their potentially beneficial pharmacological activities and a wide variation in their modes of bonding and stereochemistry^{1,2}. Macrocyclic complexes have received a great attention because of their biological activities including antitumour, antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral and anticarcinogenic³⁻⁶ activities. Such biological activities are due to their ability to form tetradentate chelate with essential heavy metal ions bonding through sulphur and nitrogen⁷. In addition to this, they were screened for their medicinal activities because they possess some cytotoxic effect. They also stabilize uncommon oxidation states, generate a different coordination number in transition metal complexes in order to participate in various redox reactions⁸. Chromium(III) has biological effects including carcinogenicity and variety of allergic response⁹. Internuclear reduction of carcinogenic chromium(IV) generates chromium DNA adducts.

Chromium(III) DNA plays an important role in mutagenesis¹⁰. Manganese(II) and its compounds were widely used in analytical chemistry, metallurgical processes, paint and pigments industry^{11,12}. The complexes of manganese(II) with macrocyclic ligands play an excellent role in catalytic and biological process¹³⁻¹⁵. In this paper, we report the synthesis, spectral characterization and biological screening of Cr^{III} and Mn^{II} complexes with a tetradentate macrocyclic ligand (L) derived from thiosemicarbazide and furil (Scheme 1).

Results and discussion

The analytical and physical properties of the prepared compounds are given in Table 1. Chromium(III) complexes are 1 : 1 electrolytes (90–102 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹). However, the molar conductance data of the Mn^{II} complexes lies in the range 8–10 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ indicating the non-electrolytic nature¹⁶. Thus these complexes may be formulated as [Cr(L)X₂]X and [Mn(L)X₂], respectively [where X = Cl⁻ and NO₃⁻].

Scheme 1. Synthesis of ligand (L).

Mass spectra of ligand and complexes :

The mass spectrum of the ligand (Fig. 1) shows a peak at m/z 490 (57%), which is corresponding to the M^+ (parental ion). The peaks at m/z 423, 356, 289 and 222 amu are due to the stepwise removal of the four C_4H_3O groups from the macrocyclic ligand. The inten-

sity of the peak at 222 amu is 70% because it corresponds to the macrocyclic moiety. It also shows series of peaks at 16, 44, 53, 81, 109, 141 and 178 amu corresponding to various fragments. The intensities of these peaks give the idea of the stability of the fragments.

In the mass spectrum (Fig. 2) of $[Cr(L)Cl_2]Cl$ complex molecular ion (M^+) peak is observed at m/z 650 amu corresponding to macrocyclic species $[Cr(L)Cl_2]Cl^-$, confirm the proposed formula. It also shows series of peaks at 16, 36, 71, 107, 257, 293, 328, 360, 395, 458, 494, 527, 562, 614 and 634 amu corresponding to various fragments. The intensities of these peaks give the idea of the stability of the fragments.

IR spectra of ligand and complexes :

IR spectrum of the ligand (L) does not exhibit any band corresponding for the free primary diamine and ketonic group. In the IR spectrum of ligand a band appeared at 1580 cm^{-1} attributed to $\nu(C=N)$ group. The position of this band is shifted towards lower side in the spectra of the complexes indicate that coordination takes place through the nitrogen atoms of $\nu(C=N)$ group. The coordination of the metal ions with nitrogen atom is also confirmed by presence the $\nu(M-N)$ and at $430\text{--}493\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The position of $\nu(C=S)$ band observed at 827 cm^{-1} in spectrum of ligand remains unchanged in complexes. It suggests that sulphur is not involved in coordination^{17,18}.

Further, the complexes show the additional bands due to the coordinated anions. The bands at $280\text{--}320\text{ cm}^{-1}$

Table 1. Molar conductance and elemental analysis data for ligand (L) and its Cr^{III} and Mn^{II} complexes

Comps.	Colour	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Solvent used
				C	H	N	M		
L	Almond	60	236	54.00	2.90	17.56	-	-	
$C_{22}H_{14}N_6O_4S_2$			(53.87)	(2.85)	(17.14)				
$[Cr(L)Cl_2]Cl$	Dull green	65	250	40.74	2.16	12.96	8.32	DMSO	
$CrC_{22}H_{14}N_6O_4S_2Cl_3$			(40.64)	(2.15)	(12.93)	(8.16)			
$[Cr(L)(NO_3)_2]NO_3$	Green	62	265	36.29	1.95	17.34	7.30	DMSO	
$CrC_{22}H_{14}N_9O_{13}S_2$			(36.21)	(1.92)	(17.28)	(7.27)			
$[Mn(L)Cl_2]$	White	59	271	42.92	2.30	13.69	8.98	DMSO	
$MnC_{22}H_{14}N_6O_4S_2Cl_2$			(42.85)	(2.27)	(13.63)	(8.92)			
$[Mn(L)(NO_3)_2]$	White	55	282	39.50	2.13	16.77	8.27	DMSO	
$MnC_{22}H_{14}N_8O_{10}S_2$			(39.46)	(2.09)	(16.74)	(8.22)			

Fig. 1. Electronic impact mass spectrum of the ligand (L).

Fig. 2. Electronic impact mass spectrum of the complex $[\text{Cr}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$.

due to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{Cl})$ are present in chloro complexes. The nitrate complexes show IR bands at $1420-1448$ (ν_5), $1317-1321$ (ν_1) and $1023-1077$ (ν_2). The ν_5 and ν_1 NO_3 stretching vibrations are separated by $101-131$ cm^{-1} which

suggests the unidentate²⁰ coordination nature of NO_3^- . However, in Cr^{III} complexes a band is also present at 1394 cm^{-1} which suggests the presence of uncoordinated nitrate.

Magnetic moment and electronic spectra :

Chromium(III) complexes show magnetic moment in the range $3.82-3.87$ B.M. at room temperature, corresponding to three unpaired electrons (Table 2). The electronic spectra (Fig. 3 (A-B)) of Cr^{III} complexes recorded in DMSO solution. These complexes display three electronic spectral bands in the range of $18582-18608$, $22284-22368$ and $24910-24938$ cm^{-1} , characteristic to an octahedral geometry²¹. The bands may be assigned to transitions : ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F) \nu_1$, ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F) \nu_2$ and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P) \nu_3$, respectively. Various ligand field parameters were calculated²² and listed in Table 3. The first spin allowed transition directly gives the value of $10 Dq$. The

Table 2. Magnetic moment and electronic spectral data (cm^{-1}) of the complexes

Complex	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	λ_{max} (cm^{-1})	($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	Solvent used
$[\text{Cr}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$	3.82	18582, 22284, 24910	40, 55, 62	DMSO
$[\text{Cr}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	3.87	18608, 22368, 24938	43, 52, 60	DMSO
$[\text{Mn}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	6.01	17898, 22966, 27126, 36319	45, 54, 61, 73	DMSO
$[\text{Mn}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	5.98	18310, 22776, 27434, 38173	46, 56, 63, 75	DMSO

Fig. 3. Electronic spectra of the complexes : (A) $[\text{Cr}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$, (B) $[\text{Cr}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$, (C) $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$ and (D) $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$.

Racah interelectronic repulsion parameter (B) is calculated from the equation :

$$B = (2v_1^2 + v_2^2 - 3v_1v_2)/(15v_2 - 27v_1)$$

The nephelauxetic parameter β was calculated by the relation : $\beta = B(\text{complex})/B(\text{free ion})$, where $B(\text{free ion})$ is 918 cm^{-1} for Cr^{III} . The β values indicate that there is an appreciable covalent character in the metal-ligand σ bond.

At room temperature the magnetic moment of Mn^{II} complexes lies in the range 5.98–6.01 B.M., corresponding to five unpaired electrons, as expected for high spin d^5 system. Electronic spectra of Mn^{II} complexes (Fig. 3 (C-D)) exhibit four absorption bands in the range 17898–

18310, 22776–22966, 27126–27434 and $36319\text{--}38173 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. These bands may be assigned to the following transitions²³ : ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} ({}^4G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^4A_{1g} ({}^4G)$, $(10B+5C)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g ({}^4d)$, $(17B+5C)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} ({}^4P)$, $(7B+5C)$, respectively. The ligand field parameter values Dq , B , C and β for Mn^{II} are calculated²⁴ and listed in Table 3. The numerical value of 786 cm^{-1} for B for the Mn^{II} free ion is used to calculate the value of β . The observed values for parameter β suggest that the complexes have appreciable ionic character.

EPR spectra :

EPR spectra of the Cr^{III} complexes were recorded at

Table 3. Ligand field parameters and EPR spectral data of the complexes

Complex	Dq (cm^{-1})	B (cm^{-1})	C (cm^{-1})	β	LFSE (kJ mol^{-1})	EPR spectral data at RT	
						g_{iso}	\AA
$[\text{Cr}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$	1858	425	1700	0.46	175.6	2.0001	–
$[\text{Cr}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	1860	429	1716	0.47	177.8	2.0004	–
$[\text{Mn}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	820	746	2984	0.94	–	1.9998	109.65
$[\text{Mn}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	839	763	3052	0.97	–	2.0018	112.85

Fig. 4. EPR spectra of the complexes : (A) $[Mn(L)Cl_2]$ as polycrystalline and (B) $[Mn(L)Cl_2]$ in DMSO solution.

room temperature as polycrystalline sample. The X-band EPR spectra of all the Cr^{III} complexes in solid state show a broad signal in the vicinity of $g_{iso} \approx 2.0$. Due to large line widths and dominance of $g_{iso} \approx 2.0$ peaks, no hyperfine splitting is observed and the estimation of parameters D and E is not possible. The g_{iso} values lies in the range 2.001–2.004 and are given in Table 3.

EPR spectra of Mn^{II} complexes were recorded at room temperature as polycrystalline sample and in solution of DMF (Fig. 4 (A-B)). The polycrystalline spectra were isotropic and exhibit the 'g' value in the range 1.9998–2.0018 (Table 3). In DMSO solution Mn^{II} complexes show EPR spectra containing the six lines arising due to the hyperfine interaction between the unpaired electron with the ^{55}Mn nuclear ($I = 5/2$). The nuclear magnetic quantum number M_I , corresponding to these lines are $-5/2$, $-3/2$, $-1/2$, $+1/2$, $+3/2$ and $+5/2$ from low to the high field (Table 3).

Structure of the complexes :

On the basis of above spectral studies the following structure may be suggested for the complexes (Fig. 5).

Antifungal studies :

In all the test fungus studied (Fig. 6) antifungal activity increased with the increasing concentration of the test compounds. The activity of the compounds are in the following order : furil < thiosemicarbazide < L < Cr^{III}

[where $M = Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}$, $X = Cl^-, NO_3^-$ and $n = 1$ for Cr^{III} and 0 for Mn^{II}]

Fig. 5. Proposed structure of the complexes.

< Mn^{II} . The data (Table 4, Fig. 7) reveals that the metal complexes are more active as compared to free metal salts as well as ligand. The chelation theory²⁵ accounts for the increased activity of the metal complexes. The chelation reduces the polarity of the metal atom mainly because of the partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor groups and possible p electron delocalization with in the whole chelation ring. The chelation ring increases the

Fig. 6. Antifungal activities of the compounds against *Rhizoctonia bataticola* : (A) Ligand, (B) $[\text{Cr}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ and (C) $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$.

Table 4. Antifungal screening data of the compounds

Sl. no.	Compds.	Fungal inhibition (%) (conc. in $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)					
		<i>Aspergillus niger</i>		<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>		<i>Rhizoctonia bataticola</i>	
		125	250	125	250	125	250
1.	Furil	-	12	15	22	-	15
2.	Thiosemicarbazide	15	22	22	29	-	17
3.	L	17	25	28	34	20	32
4.	$[\text{Cr}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$	29	36	35	41	25	45
5.	$[\text{Cr}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	27	42	34	43	30	42
6.	$[\text{Mn}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	37	48	45	56	51	72
7.	$[\text{Mn}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	42	55	49	62	46	55
8.	Chlorothalonil (standard)	45	69	54	70	62	85

lipophilic nature of the central atom which subsequently favours its permeation through the lipid layer of the cell membrane²⁶. The enhanced activity of the complexes can also be explained on the basis of their high solubility, fineness of the particles, size of the metal ion and the presence of bulkier organic moieties.

Experimental

All the chemicals and solvents used were of AnalaR

grade and procured from Sigma-Aldrich and Fluka. Metal salts were purchased from E. Merck and were used as received.

Synthesis of ligand :

A hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of thiosemicarbazide (1.82 g, 0.02 mol) and an ethanolic solution (20 mL) of furil (3.82 g, 0.02 mol) were mixed slowly with constant stirring. This mixture was refluxed at 85 °C for 6–8 h.

Fig. 7. Antifungal screening of the compounds at (A) 125 ppm and (B) 250 ppm.

On cooling, a almond coloured compound was precipitated out. It was filtered, washed with cold EtOH and dried under vacuum over P_4O_{10} .

Synthesis of complexes :

Hot ethanolic solutions (20 mL) of the corresponding metal salts (0.01 mol) were mixed with a hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of the ligand (0.01 mol). The reaction mixture was refluxed at 80 °C for 10–12 h. On cooling, a coloured compound was precipitated out in each case. The compound was filtered, washed with cold ethanol and dried under vacuum over P_4O_{10} .

Physical measurements :

C, H and N were analyzed on a Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer. Molar conductance was measured on the ELICO (CM82T) conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance using $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ as a calibrant. Electron impact mass spectrum was recorded on JEOL, JMS, DX-

303 mass spectrometer. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on FTIR spectrum BX-II spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were recorded in DMSO on Shimadzu UV mini-1240 spectrophotometer. EPR spectra of the complexes were recorded as polycrystalline sample at room temperature on E_4 -EPR spectrometer using the DPPH as the *g*-marker.

Antifungal screening :

The preliminary fungitoxicity screening of the compounds at different concentrations were performed *in vitro* against the test fungi, *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Rhizoctonia bataticola* by the Food Poison Method^{27,28}. Stock solutions of compounds were prepared by dissolving the compounds in DMSO. Chlorothalonil used as commercial fungicide and DMSO served as control. Potato dextrose agar medium was prepared by using potato, dextrose, agar-agar and distilled water. Appropriate quantities of the compounds in DMF was added to potato dextrose agar medium in order to get a concentrations of 250 and 125 ppm of compound in the medium. The medium was poured into a set of two petriplates under aseptic conditions in a laminar flow hood. When the medium in the plates was solidified, a mycelial discs of 0.5 cm in diameter cut from the periphery of the 7 days old culture and it was aseptically inoculated upside down in the centre of the petriplates. These treated petriplates were incubated at 26 ± 1 °C until fungal growth in the control petriplates was almost complete.

The mycelial growth of fungi (mm) in each petriplates was measured diametrically and growth inhibition (*I*) were calculated by using the formula :

$$I (\%) = \frac{C - T}{C} \times 100$$

where *C* is the growth of the fungus (mm) in control and *t* is the growth of test compounds.

Conclusions :

The IR, UV and EPR spectral studies lead to the conclusion that the chromium(III) and manganese(II) complexes show the octahedral geometry with tetradentate ligand coordinated through the nitrogen atom of $\nu(C=N)$ groups and the anions occupied axial positions. The results of fungicidal activity show that metal complexes are more active as compared to free ligand.

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